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Artistic Expression Of Historical Facts In The Work "Starry Nights" By The Writer Pirimkul Kadyrov

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Abstract: this article explores the artistic expression of historical facts in Pirimkul Kadyrov's "Starry Nights". In particular, the extent to which historical facts were introduced into the work through artistic similes, speech of characters, art of antithesis, satire, humor, and artistic coloring is studied. When writing the work, the writer mainly used the memoir "Baburnoma" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur, so these two works are comparatively analyzed.

Keywords: Starry nights, Boburnoma, historical facts, artistic expression, artistic work, simile art, character speech, antithesis art, satire, humor, artistic painting.

INTRODUCTION

The fact that few historical works have been created in Uzbek literature in recent years indicates that the principle of documentary is a priority in it. The fact that the plot of a work of art cannot leave the framework of historical facts, and that the development of events for the writer is within the scope of the source, requires great creative skill from the creator in creating such works.

The main aspect of the historical work is that the creative reader should illuminate the spirit of that time before the eyes of the reader, convincingly reveal the fate of the historical person, the scene of the historical struggle of the time.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Pirimkul Kadirov wrote his work on biographical information about the life and creative activity of Babur – the memoir "Boburnoma" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur; Gulbadan Beg's "Humoyunname", historical sources – "Tarihi Olam Oro'i Abbasi", "Habib us-siyar" by Khondamir; based on documentary materials about Babur from different periods. In the work, Babur's image as a just king and a talented poet devoted to Navoi, as a potential general, was revealed step by step throughout the

work. Not only revealed, but the episodes related to the writing of the poet's ghazals, the creation of the memoir "Boburnoma" are presented, such scenes indicate that the writer reliably expressed the historical truth in artistic forms.

It is known that Pirmkul Kadyrov used Babur's memoir "Boburnoma"¹ as the main source when writing the historical novel "Starry Nights". The fact that Babur's memoir "Boburnoma" and Pirmkul Kadyrov's historical novel "Starry Nights" began with the events of 1494 AD (899 Hijri) is the first proof of our opinion.

DISCUSSION

In the first pages of "Boburnoma" it is mentioned that he made a cell in the hard-to-climb rock of Mount Barokoh in Osh:

"There are many voices about Osh's virtue. A beautiful mountain called Barokoh rises in the south-east of Kurgani. Sultan Mahmud Khan built a cell on the top of this mountain. Below that cell, at the top of this mountain, in the nine hundred and second year (1497), I built a cell with a porch. Although that cell is higher, this cell is also raised in many good places: whole cities and neighborhoods are visible like this. (page 29)

This information is from the work "Starry Nights": "Osh. Salvation order?² in the chapter, the details of the building process of the cell, the appearance of the cell are given with artistic drawings, and the fate of the cell in the following centuries is also given by the author in the form of a comment. Also, the name of Baroko'h mountain mentioned in "Boburnoma" was included in the work by Pirmkul Kadirov with another name in the vernacular - Buratog'.

One of the main characters in "Starry Nights", Babur's most trusted beg - Kasimbek Kavchin, has a lot of good thoughts in "Boburnoma":

"...Until the end of his life, his discretion and attention increased, did not decrease. He was a brave man." (page 36)

However, even this most trusted beki left Babur in difficult times: *"...When I rode from Mascho mountains towards Sultan Mahmud Khan, Qasimbek left and went towards Khisravshah. In the nine hundred and tenth year (1504), I defeated Khisravshah and besieged Muqim in Kabul. At this time, Kasimbek arrived. I paid attention and mercy as before." (page 36)*

The above facts are illustrated in the work "Starry Nights" as follows: *"Babur stood up to say goodbye to Kasimbek. Babur, who had lost his beloved sister in Samarkand and his wife in Tashkent, and today, after hearing so many ominous news, he was forced to part with his most trusted bey, no matter how hard he tried to keep himself calm, his knees buckled and staggered. As Kasimbek hugged him goodbye, his eyes filled with tears." (page 273)*

Babur writes in "Boburnoma" about Ayesha Beg, who was betrothed to him since childhood, was his first wife and later divorced:

"The daughter of Sultan Ahmed Mirza, Ayesha Sultanbegim, was promised to me by her father and uncle when she was alive. When she came to Khojand, I took her in the month of Sha'ban. When I first got married, although my love was not bad, it was my first marriage, and out of modesty and shyness,

¹ Z. M. Bobur. Boburnoma. – T.: O'qituvchi, 2008 y.

² Qodirov P. Yulduzli tunlar. T.: Sharq, 2016. – page 73.

I went every ten, fifteen, twenty days. After that, there was no more affection, but hesitance became even more: in a month and forty days, my mother sent me requests and worries." (page 73)

Based on the above information, Babur's feelings towards Ayesha Beg are illustrated by Pirimkul Kadirov as a "misinterpreted dream" in "Starry Nights":

"Once upon a time, when he was in love with Ayesha Beg without seeing her, the ghazals he used to write at her feet now seemed to Babur like a dream with a wrong interpretation... He didn't miss Ayesha Beg even if he didn't see her for months... even so, he treated Ayesha Beg as well as possible. ...» (p. 225)

One such beautiful artistic simile is related to the image of Zuhra Begum, the mother of Sultan Ali Mirza. In "Boburnoma" there are such writings about Zuhra Begim:

"...This unfortunate woman (Zuhra Begi) betrayed her son's mistress because she was in a bad mood and wanted to touch the ground. Shaibani Khan did not care for him at all. Maybe a woman of the harem, a maid-servant, did not even notice". (p. 76)

Pirimkul Kadyrov makes the above information even more impressive through the author's speech, using the art of tazad:

"Zuhra Beg's face was not clearly visible behind the white silk net. Khan looked at her hands with golden rings with jewel eyes. These trembling hands, with bulging veins, indicated that the lady was very old. Shaibani Khan remembered his nineteen-year-old wife, whom he recently married in Bukhara. Then Zuhra Beg's eldest son Sultan Ali Mirza passed by." (page 198)

In this artistic interpretation, the nineteen-year-old young wife of Shaibani Khan, whom Shaibani Khan married in Bukhara, is opposed to Begum Zuhra with trembling hands, whose veins are bulging, and the impressiveness is increased.

It can be seen that Pirimkul Kadirov introduced the facts presented in "Boburnoma" not only through the speech of the author, but also through the speech of the characters. For example, Sultan Mahmud Mirza is described in "Boburnoma":

"He was busy with violence and depravity, he drank alcohol all the time. Many bachcha saks, wherever there were beautiful teenagers in the places under his control, he brought them in various ways and made them bachcha. He used to take care of the sons and cousins of the Beks, and he even ordered this service to the one born from his cousin. This custom was so popular that there was no one without a child. They considered paederasty to be a profession. They blamed not taking care of the children. Because of oppression and corruption, all his sons died young." (page 44)

We find this information in the speech of Muhammad Salih in the work "Starry Nights" by Shaybani Khan with his army chief and ayons over Sultan Ali Mirza and Khoja Yahya:

" – The fault is not only with this young Mirza," Muhammad Salih objected to him. – His father, Mahmud Mirza, was a corrupt person without faith. When he was king in Samarkand, he was not satisfied with womanizing, but also brought paederasty to its peak. The poor people were afraid to let their handsome young boys go out, so they hid them inside like they hid their girls. (page 204)

The presentation of the above fact not through the speech of the author, but through the speech of the character - from the language of Muhammad Salih, was one of the achievements in terms of the impressiveness of the artistic image. In addition, the simile here, such as "hiding beautiful young boys inside, like hiding girls" has increased the artistic power of the work to some extent.

Let's look at the negative facts about the wife of Sultan Husayn Mirza, Khadija Begum, presented in "Boburnoma" and the manner in which the characters in "Starry Nights" are presented:

"...She rose from the rank of a temporary wife to the rank of a begum. Later, she was the main lady. Muhammad Momin Mirza was killed by his efforts. The sons of Sultan Husain Mirza became enemies to each other. Mostly because of this woman. She pretended to be smart, but she was a foolish and chatterer woman. She is also a Rofiziya (Shia)..." ("Baburnoma", p. 132)

The artistic expression of the above inscription in "Starry Nights" is reflected in the dialogue between Ubaydulla Sultan and Khadija Begum:

"- After all, I am also from the royal family!" What kind of humiliation is this?!

- You are from the Rafizi family! Punishing the rapists is a reward!

- Mr. Sultan, you have an old mother like me. At least respect my motherhood!..

- My mother did not do the evil things you did! Which mother killed her own grandson?! You are one of the murderers who caused the death of your grandson Momin Mirza!

The glorious and proud face of Khadija Beg suddenly became pitiful, her waist was bent and her hands were hanging down". (p. 350)

Above, Pirimkul Kadirov could have mentioned the facts about Begum Khadichha in "Boburnoma" in this way, but the writer draws the lines of Begum Khadichha, firstly, through the language of the characters, and secondly, represents by comparing and contrasting two mothers, that is, Begum Khadichha and the mother of Ubaidulla Sultan. In this way, the writer reveals the secrets of Khadija Beg.

In addition, there is another series of information that is brought to life in "Starry Nights" extensively and in detail. For example, the images of Badiuzzaman Mirza and Muzaffar Mirza fleeing Herat to Shaibani Khan:

"Mirzas' mothers, sisters, wives, and treasure were all in Ikhtiyoriddin's fortress, known as Olaqorgan. Mirzas reach the city late. They rest their horses until midnight and sleep. They leave the city in the morning. They cannot imagine closing the fortress. At such a time and opportunity, they leave their mothers and sisters and children to the Uzbek captivity without taking them out. They didn't even think of strengthening the fortress." (page 156)

Pirimkul Kadirov describes the cowardice of Badiuzzamon and Muzaffar mirzas and their path with satire, i.e. mixed with bitter laughter, as follows:

"Mirza Badiuzzaman, who escaped from the battlefield, reached Herat before everyone else, but did not enter the city. Then he stopped for a few hours in Bogi Jahanoro, rested his horses, and took as much gold, silver and jewels as he could carry. His wife and children were inside the city - in the arch. Mirza Badiuzzamon, who was afraid of the danger of the devil chasing after him, called the city council and ordered to close the gates of the castle. "Don't be afraid to stay in the siege, we will gather an army from Kandahar and rescue you," he left his wives and children in the fortress and rushed south.

Arriving at Herat at night, Muzaffar mirza acted as if he was competing with his brother even in overcoming and escaping. He also stopped for a few hours in Bogi Safida outside the city to catch his breath, took the most necessary things and did not enter the arch, fearing that it would be lost. He left his

mother and wives inside the castle and ordered to close the gates, and he also said, "If you stay under siege, I will come and save you!" ran away towards Astrobod. (pages 338-339)

Shaibani Khan's conquest of Herat and his actions are described in "Boburnoma" in sharp colors:

"After Shaybak Khan took Herat, he did bad things to the descendants of these kings, not only to this community, but to the whole people. This man from the village and the world, who has not seen the world, earned such a bad name for the five-day world. Shaybaq Khan's ugly behavior and misdeeds happened in Herat: first of all, for the sake of the rotten world, he handed over Khadija Begum to Shah Mansur Bakhshi ... and subjected her to various torments. And he entrusted a noble and dear person like Sheikh Puron to the Mongol Abdul-Wahhab, he entrusted each of his sons to another person, and he entrusted his poetry and talent to Mulla Binai..."

Again, Muzaffar took Mirza's wife named Khanzodabegim as his wife, without paying attention to the iddah period, as soon as he took Herat. Qazi Ikhtiyar also gave a lesson in tafsir to Muhammad Mir Yusuf, one of the famous and talented mullahs of Herat, despite being a poor man himself. Again, Mulla Sultan Ali Mashhadi touched the picture and letter of the artist Behzad with a pen and made corrections. Every few days, he would write a silly verse and recite it on the pulpit, hang it on the altar, and receive gifts from the townspeople. Although Shaibani Khan was a morning person, who did not miss the five-time prayer, and knew the science of recitation, but such silly, stupid, unbelieving words and deeds happened more than him. (page 156)

Pirimkul Kadirov brings these details into the work "Starry Nights" in a "softer" way, while explaining the details, the writer tries to look at them from different perspectives, including the author's position. In this case, the author's position is evident in his refraining from drawing the lines of Shaibani Khan in very dark colors. For example, as a scheming woman who caused the death of her grandson Momin Mirza, who deserved such punishment (p. 350), it seems that Shaibani Khan's "handover of Khadija Begim to Shah Mansur Bakhshi for the sake of the rotten world, and subjected her to various sufferings" is somewhat justified.

Or that "Muzaffar Mirza married the woman named after Khanzada Begim as soon as he took Herat, regardless of the iddah period, and "Karakoz Begim accepted the ghazal of Khan, who was enraged because Muzaffar Mirza abandoned his wives as a coward" (p. 339), it can also be seen that Shaibani Khan tried to justify and justify through his dialogue with Shaykhulislam and Qazi, the leaders of sharia:

"Korakoz Begum was married to Mirza Muzaffar. It has not been five days since her husband left her. However, the wife in the marriage of a Muslim is Iddah, and it is not possible to marry another person until three months have passed. Sharia strictly forbids it.

Shaykhulislam kissed the carpet under Khan's feet and started talking about it, when the Khan interrupted him:

- Don't teach us Sharia! Begum's handsome husband divorced her four months ago. You say three months! Begum was without a husband for four months! Aren't you, Sharia leaders, unaware of this?!

Shaykhulislam, who was afraid of Khan's anger, rubbed his white beard on the Mahfuri carpet and kissed the ground again.

- We are aware, my lord!

- *We are aware!* - said the judge kissing the carpet. They knew that Muzaffar Mirza divorced his wife four months ago. However, when the mirza reconciled with his wife again, Shaykhulislam and Qazi remarried Begim to her husband. But to tell this to the khan, who was jealous of the mention of the Beg's former young husband, was tantamount to accepting death.

The leaders of Sharia are now preparing to read marriages without making a fuss about it..." (p. 340)

Pirimkul Kadirov brought the historical truth into the work, and when he brought it, he was able to bring it in without burning the sikh or the kebab: although Shaibani Khan was opposed to Babur, but he was not inferior to Babur, it is known from a number of historical sources that he was a man of knowledge and strong religious knowledge. It is said that he married Muzaffar Mirza's wife, whose Iddah period had not yet expired. But detailed details about this cannot be found in historical works. Accordingly, the writer describes Shaibani Khan didn't know that Muzaffar Mirza's remarriage of Karakoz Begum; fearing to tell the truth because *"being jealous of the mention of the Begum's previous young husband, telling this to the khan whose cup of patience is full is tantamount to accepting death"* describes and refrains from representing both sides in completely black colors.

The description of relationship between Karakozbegim and Shaibani Khan in "Starry Nights" is also noteworthy:

"Once the door of the hall was opened with a bang, and Shaibani Khan came out, dressed in a white turban on his head tilted to one side. Her complexion is faded, her lips quiver.

- It's obscene! It's broken! Impudent!..

... As it turns out, Karakozbegim does an extravagant act, which the last kings of Herat love and the women of the upper class call "galvira". With this, she wants to admire the fifty-six-year-old Khan, and also to increase his inspiration. However, the khan, who has been married many times and slept with many young women, has never seen such tricks in his life. At first he is confused, then he remembers Karakozbegim's former young husband. He brings to mind the fact that Begum did such tricks to her previous husband, he gets disappointed and swears and gets up. (p. 341)

The writer expresses the above artistic images through humor. In addition, in "Boburnoma" Shaibani Khan's *"touching and reforming the image and letter of the painter Behzad with Mulla Sultan Ali Mashhadi"* is also included in the work through humor. (pages 346-347-348 in the work) The writer does not allow hatred towards Shaibani Khan to form in the heart of the reader.

Although Pirimkul Kadirov used "Boburnoma" as the main source when writing "Starry Nights", he does not ignore other historical sources. For example, let's take the images of the death of Shaibani Khan in the work:

"The victors cut off Shaibani Khan's head, pierced it with a spear and threw it under the foot of the horse on which Shah Ismail was riding. Then the red-headed people removed the skin from Shaibani Khan's severed head and stuffed it with straw. The Turkish sultan Bayezid II was one of the Sunnis persecuting the Shias in the West and inflicting pain on Shah Ismail. Shah Ismail sent Shaybani Khan's straw-stuffed head to the Turkish sultan as a "gift" in the meaning: "Look at the fate of the Sunnis who are enmity with me!"

The Sunni-Shia enmity reached such a level that the red-headed people were not satisfied with this, they covered Shaibani Khan's skull with gold and made a drinking cup out of it." (page 359)

The above unbelievable details would have been thought to be exaggerations if they were written down by the enemies of Shah Ismail. However, these details are given in "History of the World Abbasi" written by the well-wishers of Shah Ismail, including in the work "Habib us-siyar" by Khondamir.

RESULTS

Having studied the artistic expression of historical facts in Pirimkul Kadyrov's work "Starry Nights", we obtained the following results:

1. Pirimkul Kadirov, when writing the work "Starry Nights", mainly relied on the memoir "Boburnoma" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur.

2. The writer's success lies in the fact that he was very careful in depicting the black pages of history in his work, that is, he brought historical facts into his work in a somewhat "softer" way: he used humor and satire; in covering the details, the writer tried to look at it from different angles, including the author's position. In this case, the author's position was evident in his refraining from drawing negative characters in extremely dark colors.

3. The writer included the facts from the memoir "Boburnoma" in "Starry Nights" not only through the author's speech, but also through the speech and dialogues of the characters, which served to increase the effectiveness of this artistic-historical work.

4. The writer gave the details in "Boburnoma" using the art of antithesis, through which the image and character of events and persons became even brighter.

CONCLUSION

The writer Pirimkul Kadirov brought the historical truth into the work, and when he brought it, he was able to bring it in without burning the sikh or the kebab: although Shaibani Khan is opposed to Babur, it is known from a number of historical sources that he, like Babur, was a scholar and had a strong religious knowledge. Although the writer used "Boburnoma" as the main source when writing the work, unlike "Boburnoma", in "Starry Nights" Shaibaniykhani's personality is not completely painted in black colors. It is in this respect that the work is commendable.

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